

SIMULATION OF TEXTILE COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENT USING ROTATION FREE SHELL FINITE ELEMENT

P. Wang¹, N. Hamila^{1*}, P. Boisse¹

¹ Universite de Lyon, INSA-Lyon, LaMCoS, CNRS UMR 5259, F-69621, France

* Corresponding author(nahiene.hamila@insa-lyon.fr)

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1 Introduction

Numerical optimization of products and production processes becomes increasingly important in the design phase of composite structures. Numerical simulations of the composite forming processes are an essential part of these optimization tools. They permit to determine the conditions of the feasibility of a process without defect (wrinkling, fracture of yarns, porosities...) but above all, they give the fibre orientations after shaping. This is mainly important because redistribution of the fibres is inevitable when double curved products are considered. The fibre orientations strongly influence the mechanical behaviour of the final part and the permeability of the reinforcement and thus the injection of the resin in the case of a liquid moulding process [1].

For a physical analysis of a composite forming process, the complete model must include all the equations for the mechanics, especially equilibrium, constitutive equations, and boundary conditions. These equations must be solved numerically, with some approximations. Finite Element analysis of the composite forming process includes the tools modelling, the contact and friction between the different parts, and above all, the mechanical behaviour of the composite during forming. If these models are numerically costly, problems of computation time are steadily reduced through improved processing capabilities. The main problem for the FE approach therefore lies in the requirement for accurate models of all the significant aspects of the forming process.

2 Mechanical Model

2.1 Mechanical Behavior

Textile composite reinforcements considered in this paper are made up of continuous fibres. The material resulting from this assembly of continuous fibres

exhibits a very specific mechanical behaviour since relative motions are possible between the yarns and the fibres. In liquid composite moulding processes (LCM), the textile reinforcement pre-forming stage takes advantage of these possible motions. The forming is made on dry reinforcement (i.e. without resin) since it is performed before the injection stage. Although the fibrous reinforcement is not strictly continuous because of relative sliding between fibres, several mechanical behaviour models have been proposed that consider the textile reinforcement as an anisotropic continuum [2]. Nevertheless there is no widely accepted model that describes accurately all of the main aspects of fabric mechanical behaviour [3]. Actually, such a model must convey the specificities of the composition of the textile made of yarns and fibres and above all take into account the variation of the properties during the forming. These changes are very large because of the variations of fibre directions and of the local lateral compression of the yarns due to the forming. The very specific mechanical behaviour of textile reinforcements has led the laboratories that analyse the composite pre-forming to develop mechanical tests that are quite specific to these materials.

2.2 Internal virtual work

Fig.1. (a) Loads on a unit woven cell and resultants:(b) tensions, (c) in-plane shear moment, (d) bending moments.

The textile composite reinforcement consists of woven unit cells. Its mechanical behaviour is

specific because of the possible relative displacements between yarns and between fibres within the yarns. Let's consider the loads on a unit woven cell such as Fig. 1a. The following resultants of these loads are considered:

- The tensions T_1 and T_2 are the resultants of the loads respectively on warp and weft yarn directions (Fig. 1b)
- The in-plane shear moment M_s is the moment at the centre of the RUC, in the direction of the normal to the fabric, resulting from the in-plane loads on the unit woven cell (Fig. 1c).
- The bending moments M_1 and M_2 resulting on the warp and weft yarns (Fig. 1d).

The principle of virtual work can be written:

$$\begin{aligned}
 W_{\text{ext}}(\underline{\eta}) - W_{\text{acc}}(\underline{\eta}) = & \\
 \sum_{p=1}^{N_c} & \underbrace{{}^p \varepsilon_{11}(\underline{\eta}) \quad {}^p T_1 \quad {}^p L_1 + {}^p \varepsilon_{22}(\underline{\eta}) \quad {}^p T_2 \quad {}^p L_2}_{(b)} + \\
 & \underbrace{\gamma(\underline{\eta}) \quad {}^p M_s}_{(c)} + \\
 & \underbrace{{}^p \chi_{11}(\underline{\eta}) \quad {}^p M_1 \quad {}^p L_1 + {}^p \chi_{22}(\underline{\eta}) \quad {}^p M_2 \quad {}^p L_2}_{(d)}
 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

3 Finite Element Formulation

Four node membrane finite elements based on this semi-discrete approach have been previously proposed [4]. The objective of the present paper is to propose a three node semi-discrete shell element including membrane and bending stiffness for textile composite reinforcement forming simulations (Fig. 2.). This bending stiffness is very small due to the fibrous nature of the textile composite reinforcement. Nevertheless this second order rigidity can be important in some cases especially when some wrinkles appear. This shell element composed of woven cells is rotational-free, i.e. the nodal variables are only displacements [5]. In a dynamic explicit approach, the membrane and bending nodal interior loads are defined according to the tensions, shear torque and bending moments given by the mechanical tests specific to textile reinforcements.

Fig.2. Triangular element and its three neighbors.

3.1 Triangular element made of woven cells

Textile composite reinforcements considered in this paper are made up of continuous fibres. The material coordinates r^1, r^2 are defined along the warp and weft directions (Figure 3). r^1 is equal to zero on M_1M_3 and is equal to 1 in M_2 . r^2 is equal to zero on M_1M_2 and is equal to 1 in M_3 . These coordinates are related to the coordinates in the reference element ξ^1 and ξ^2 . ($\xi^1=1$ in M_2 , $\xi^1=0$ in M_1 and M_3 , $\xi^2=1$ in M_3 , $\xi^2=0$ in M_1 and M_2 (Figure 3))

$$\begin{bmatrix} r^1 \\ r^2 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{1-ab} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & b \\ a & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \xi^1 \\ \xi^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

with $\xi^1=b$ in B and $\xi^2=a$ in A (Figure 3).

The material coordinates r^1, r^2 and ξ^1, ξ^2 give the material vectors:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{k}_1 &= \frac{\partial \underline{x}}{\partial r^1} & \underline{k}_2 &= \frac{\partial \underline{x}}{\partial r^2} \\ \underline{g}_1 &= \frac{\partial \underline{x}}{\partial \xi^1} & \underline{g}_2 &= \frac{\partial \underline{x}}{\partial \xi^2} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The associated contravariant vectors are defined by:

$$\underline{k}^\alpha \cdot \underline{k}_\beta = \delta^\alpha_\beta \quad \underline{g}^\alpha \cdot \underline{g}_\beta = \delta^\alpha_\beta \quad (10)$$

As the interpolation functions are the standard linear ones ($N_1 = 1 - \xi^1 - \xi^2$, $N_2 = \xi^1$, $N_3 = \xi^2$), equation (9) leads to:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{k}_1 &= \underline{AM}_2 & \underline{k}_2 &= \underline{BM}_3 \\ \underline{g}_1 &= \underline{M}_1 \underline{M}_2 & \underline{g}_2 &= \underline{M}_1 \underline{M}_3 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Fig.3. Curvilinear coordinates of the finite element.

3.2 Internal forces

At the time step i , the nodal tensile interior loads \mathbf{F}_{int}^{te} for the element under consideration are calculated according to the tensions T^{11} and T^{22} in the element. The virtual extension strains in warp and weft directions are given by the virtual symmetrical gradient:

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha\alpha}(\underline{\eta}) = \left(\underline{\nabla}^s(\underline{\eta}) \cdot \frac{\underline{k}_\alpha}{\|\underline{k}_\alpha\|} \right) \cdot \frac{\underline{k}_\alpha}{\|\underline{k}_\alpha\|} = \frac{\partial \underline{\eta}}{\partial r^\alpha} \cdot \frac{\underline{k}_\alpha}{\|\underline{k}_\alpha\|^2} = B_{\alpha ki} \eta_{ki} \quad (12)$$

α is an index taking value 1 or 2. η_k and $k_{\alpha k}$ are the component number k ($k=1$ to 3) respectively of the virtual displacement $\underline{\eta}$ and of vector $\underline{k}_{\alpha k}$ in the global frame and $\eta_{k1}, \eta_{k2}, \eta_{k3}$ the values of these virtual displacement components at nodes M_1, M_2, M_3 . $B_{\alpha k\ell}$ are the components of the virtual axial strain interpolation. Consequently, denoting n_{celle} the number of woven cells in the element under consideration, the nodal tensile interior load components are ($k=1,3, \ell = 1,3$):

$$\left(\mathbf{F}_{int}^{te} \right)_{k\ell} = n_{celle} \left(B_{1k\ell} T^{11}(\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{22}) \frac{L_1}{\|\underline{k}_1\|^2} + B_{2k\ell} T^{22}(\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{22}) \frac{L_2}{\|\underline{k}_2\|^2} \right) \quad (13)$$

with :

$$\begin{aligned} B_{1k1} &= (a-1)k_{1k} & B_{1k2} &= k_{1k} & B_{1k3} &= -ak_{1k} \\ B_{2k1} &= (b-1)k_{2k} & B_{2k2} &= -bk_{2k} & B_{2k3} &= k_{2k} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The nodal in plane shear interior loads \mathbf{F}_{int}^{se} for the element under consideration are calculated according to the shear torque C_s in the woven cells of the element. The virtual angle $\gamma(\underline{\eta})$ between warp and weft directions is given by the virtual gradient:

$$\gamma(\underline{\eta}) = \left(\underline{\nabla} \underline{\eta} \cdot \frac{\underline{k}_1}{\|\underline{k}_1\|} \right) \cdot \frac{\underline{k}_2}{\|\underline{k}_2\|} + \left(\underline{\nabla} \underline{\eta} \cdot \frac{\underline{k}_2}{\|\underline{k}_2\|} \right) \cdot \frac{\underline{k}_1}{\|\underline{k}_1\|} = B_{\gamma k\ell} \eta_{k\ell} \quad (15)$$

$B_{\gamma k\ell}$ are the components of the virtual in plane shear strain interpolation. Consequently, the nodal in plane shear interior load components are ($k=1,3, \ell = 1,3$):

$$\left(\mathbf{F}_{int}^{se} \right)_{k\ell} = n_{celle} B_{\gamma k\ell} C_s \quad (16)$$

In order to avoid to add supplementary degrees of freedom and consequently for numerical efficiency, the bending stiffness is taken into account within an approach without rotational degree of freedom [6]. In these approaches the curvatures of the element are computed from the positions and displacements of the neighbouring nodes elements (Figure 2). The curvatures are assumed to be constant in the element. The interpolations of the curvatures in warp and weft directions are now defined:

$$\chi_{\alpha\alpha}(\underline{\eta}) = Bb_{\alpha km} \eta_{km} \quad (17)$$

$m= 1$ to 6 (index of the node), $k = 1$ to 3 (index of direction of the displacement). The nodal bending interior load components are:

$$\left(F_{int}^{be}\right)_{km} = n_{celle} \left(Bb_{1km} M^{11} \frac{L_1}{\|k_1\|^2} + Bb_{2km} M^{22} \frac{L_2}{\|k_2\|^2} \right) \quad (18)$$

3 Forming simulation of an angle bracket

Fig.4. Deep drawing of tetrahedron shape. Geometry of the tools.

These forming tests have been developed by EADS company in order to test experimentally and numerically the manufacturing of an angle bracket by R.T.M. process. The shape of the part is a regular tetrahedron (Figure 4). The fabric is the G1151[®] interlock. This woven composite reinforcement has been studied within the ITOOL project [7]. Two bending rigidities are considered and specified in Figure 5. The measured value ($5 \cdot 10^{-1} \text{N}\cdot\text{mm}$) is the value obtained by the cantilever bending test (Figures 5a and 5c). In order to show the influence of the bending stiffness the simulations are performed with a higher value ($50 \text{N}\cdot\text{mm}$ Figure 5b and 5d)

The textile reinforcement is maintained on the die by six square blank holders (Figure 4). The force on each blank holder is 800N. The simulation results are given for ($0-90^\circ$) initial orientation of the yarns (Figures 5a and 5b) and ($\pm 45^\circ$) initial orientation of the yarns (Figures 5c and 5d). The geometry of the six blank holders leads to a large number of wrinkles

in the flat part of the fabric. A first main objective of the simulations is to verify that these wrinkles do not propagate to the tetrahedron part of the fabric. For this the pressure on the blank holders must be sufficient. A second important result is the shear angle field within the tetrahedron part. These angles are in the order of 20% in a large part of the tetrahedron. These angles affect the mechanical properties of the composite part obtained after injection. The deformed shapes (Figures 5a and 5c) have been shown to be in good agreement with experiments performed in the ITOOL project [7]

In Figure 5b and 5d, the simulations are performed with higher bending rigidities. The shear angles in the tetrahedron part are roughly the same but the wrinkles are much larger and less numerous. These last simulations confirm the importance of the bending stiffness regarding the number and the size of the wrinkles.

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Fig.5. (a) Initiale orientation 0-90°,
Bending stiffness 5.10^{-1} N.mm.

Fig.5. (b)Initiale orientation 0-90°,
Bending stiffness 50 N.mm.

Fig.5. (c) Initiale orientation $\pm 45^\circ$,
Bending stiffness 5.10^{-1} N.mm.

Fig.5. (d) Initiale orientation $\pm 45^\circ$,
Bending stiffness 50 N.mm.